

	Lublin	HPC2N	CTC-SP2
SJF	333.19	8.26	13.36
SJF+SchedInspector (trained on SDSC-SP2).	320.39	4.39	10.79

The comparison between SJF and SchedInspector trained on SDSC-SP2 but run on other traces. The values are the mean of absld among 50 samples, the smaller of them are the better. SchedInspector is not directly trained on corresponding traces, which means the upcoming jobs patterns are different from what it learned. However, the performance of SchedInspector is still better than the baseline.